

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE-TYPOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF SLANGS EXISTING IN ENGLISH AND AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGES

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Abstract

Language has a complex concept in historical and social signs, and to this day there are different definitions and ways of giving meaning by many scholars and linguists. Some argue that language is a biological, some psychological, and some sociological phenomenon. Language is a biological, psychological, and sociological phenomenon, playing an important role in how people communicate with each other. Language is the biggest factor that differentiates humans from other living things. Currently, there are many languages in the world, and there is no complete information about the accuracy of this number. But it is thought that there are about seven thousand languages. Today, English is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. English plays a fundamental role in diplomacy, trade, maritime, scientific and technical fields and information dissemination. In many countries, a foreign language is taught as the main language in educational institutions.

Researcher Naomi Chomsky introduced the theory of "Common Language Grammar" and emphasized the common features of different languages. There are many similarities between English and Azerbaijani languages in terms of grammatical and word-editing processes. Both languages have slang and their basic functions are the same. According to the structure of slang, its types are divided into three types: simple, correction and complex. There is a classification for independent slangs in English, but not in Azerbaijani. Studies have shown that the slangs of the two languages have similar and different aspects.

Keywords: English language, Azerbaijani language, slangs, similarities, differences

INTRODUCTION

Research on different aspects of language has aroused wide interest among linguists. Language has been analyzed from different perspectives by biological, psychological and sociological. There are many languages in the world, but the exact number has not been determined. Language plays a key role in human communication and is the main factor that differentiates humans from other living things. Slangs have attracted attention as an important object for studying language dynamics and social relations. Different characteristics and usage of slangs in English and Azerbaijani languages were investigated. Unlike vulgarisms, slangs represent more informality and help express ideas more concisely. The research is conducted in order to understand the semantic features of slangs and the dynamics of the language. A comparative analysis of slangs in English and Azerbaijani languages gives new ideas about the universality and characteristics of the language. The importance of the research is that it helps us better understand the evolution of language and human relationships. Contextual analysis, cognitive-linguistic analysis form the theoretical methodological base of the research work. With the help of this method, the onomasiological typology of slangs (being a universal and special event) is clarified.

Differences and similarities of slangs used in English and Azerbaijani languages

Language is a very complex concept that has been of interest to many scientists, researchers and linguists throughout the ages. Various definitions and concepts have been formed about language. Some scientists have

tried to explain language as a biological phenomenon, some as a psychological phenomenon, and some as a sociological phenomenon. Language is a biological, psychological, and sociological phenomenon and plays a leading role in people's communication with each other. And as many scientists have emphasized to this day, language is the biggest factor that distinguishes humans from other living things. There are many languages in the world. Despite the large number of studies carried out to date, it is still impossible to say exactly the number of languages that exist in the world. After numerous studies, this number is estimated to be around seven thousand. Today, English is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world. English language is famous in the world as the language of diplomacy, commerce, seafaring, scientific-technical and mass information. Currently, English is taught in many educational institutions as the main foreign language in our Republic.

Naomi Chomsky, a researcher of world languages, tried to point out the common features of different languages in his theory of "Universal Grammar".

As we know, the English language belongs to the inflectional language, and the Azerbaijani language belongs to the iltisagi or agglutinative language group. But despite belonging to different language groups, the grammar of these languages has similarities in many aspects. For example, the main parts of speech are the same in both languages: noun, adjective, number, verb, pronoun and adverb. Another similarity is manifested in the process of word correction. Thus, both prefixes and suffixes are used when creating a new word in both languages, etc.

The names of many scientists and researchers who conduct a comparative analysis of the modern English and Azerbaijani languages in Azerbaijan can be mentioned. O.I. Musayev, N. Valiyeva, E. Hajiyev, A. Huseynov, D. Yunusov, J. Akhundov, Z. Verdiyeva, F. Veysalov (Veysalli), N. Yusifov, S. Abdullayev, these are significantly different from each other. conducted a comparative analysis of the two languages and noted interesting facts about this topic in their scientific works.

In this part of the presented thesis, we will try to show the differences and similarities in the use of slang in these comparable languages.

This is where the first similarity between English and Azerbaijani slangs begins. Thus, both in English and in Azerbaijani, slangs are expressions and words created by certain professions and groups of people in society and understood by them. In both languages, most of the slangs belong to non-literary language, informal spoken language, but not to literary language, written language, official spoken language.

In both languages, slang can first be a neologism, then a common word, and finally an archaism, or it can take a fixed position in the language.

In both languages, the functions of slangs in the language are to show one's sincerity to the other party, to create laughter or mockery in the language, to achieve privacy and secrecy in certain groups, to avoid long expressions and to make it possible to say it more briefly, etc.

According to the structure of slangs in both English and Azerbaijani languages, they are divided into three types: simple, correct and complex. Among them, the most used ones are considered complex slangs (Musayev, 2003).

In addition to similarities in the use of slangs in the English language and slangs in the Azerbaijani language, there are also a number of different features. Thus, the slangs used in the English language are only related to the English culture, the unique way of life and thinking, everyday life, customs and traditions of the social classes of the English society. The fact that English slangs are not understood by speakers of other languages, including the Azerbaijani language, is related to these national characteristics (Abu, 2004). These national characteristics have been assimilated by English-speaking peoples over the centuries, polished in their languages and expressed the objects and concepts understood by the representatives of English-speaking societies. Naturally, the words and phrases that express these concepts and realities reflected in the way of life and thinking of English-speaking peoples are not immediately understood by the speakers of other languages, and naturally, the understanding of the meaning they carry requires some explanation. For example, the word toboggan ("a type of ski") of Hindu origin used in the American version of the English language does not have a direct lexical equivalent in the Azerbaijani language, because the object itself, that is, this type of ski, is not typical for the life of Azerbaijanis. For this reason, if it is found in the English text, the translation of this word into Azerbaijani is possible only through

description (a type of ski belonging to American Indians) (Hajiyeva, 2014).

Slang is a branch of metaphorical expressions widely used in the English language as well as in variants of the English language. These expressions are used in order to make the speech lively, emotional, effective, and expressive, and because they are distinguished by their conciseness and brevity, they are used by large groups of the English-speaking population and are widely represented in the vocabulary of the English language due to their artistic features. The noted artistic and linguistic importance of slangs opened the way for their in-depth study in Western linguistics and led to the emergence of dictionaries covering slangisms in English-speaking countries. This fact is another nuance that distinguishes slangs in English from slangs in the Azerbaijani language, which is that slangs in the Azerbaijani language have not been studied extensively and dictionaries have not been developed (Boase-Beier, 2004).

Another difference between slangs in the Azerbaijani and English languages is related to their classification, while in English there are general and special types of slangs, there is no such classification in the Azerbaijani language (Hajiyeva, Nacafova, Jafarov, 2014).

There are five types of slangs in English: lively and creative slangs, flippant (non-serious slangs), imitation slangs, slangs created as a result of abbreviations, slangs created by cutting words. Although this division is not carried out in the Azerbaijani language, when we look at the language, we can determine that this division is a common feature for slangs in the Azerbaijani language.

Today, the use of slangs, whether in English or in Azerbaijani, is more noticeable on Internet pages, computer games, that is, in areas related to the development of technology. This is explained by the fact that nowadays the capabilities of the computer have reached such a limit that when using it, people often forget that they are communicating with a machine or an ordinary person. Because in some cases, these machines become a better employee for people than a person. Thus, today, the scope of slang usage is more widespread in the Internet and computer field.

Most of the slangs that are common in the English language on the Internet are acronyms that are the result of shortening words related to quick correspondence. For example, b4 – Before, BBS – Be Back Soon, bf – Boyfriend, BTW – By The Way, DIKU – Do I Know You?), F2F – Face To Face, FAQ – Frequently Asked Question, HAGD – Have a Good Day, L8R – Later, LOL – Laughing Out Loud, SPST - Same Place, Same Time, SYL - See You Later, TC - Take Care, TTYL - Talk To You Later, etc. this list can be extended.

Most of the slangs used in the Internet in the Azerbaijani language consist of borrowed words, some of them are shortened versions of words. For example, admin, link, update, virus eater, online, etc. such words are included in the slang related to this field. Here, the word admin is a shortened version of the word administrator, and it is correct to consider it as slang, as it is known only to people who know this field. Link, up-

date, online are borrowed words and expressions understood by those interested in this field. The word virus eater is used as a substitute for the word antivirus. Examples of slang used by young people nowadays for quick correspondence are: cvb – cavab (reply), uni – universitet (university), tqk – təşəkkürlər (thank you), tmm – tamam (ok), slm – salam (hello), etc. it's like this.

In English, slang words were originally created by the lower social classes, such as criminals, thieves, and beggars. For example, if someone uses the phrase "blowing the peter," the meaning of the phrase is that the environment is safe for theft. If someone says they want to buy some "happy dust", that means they want to buy some cocaine. "Jail arithmetic," literally translated as "həbs hesabı" is slang for an accountant or banker who embezzles money and tries to cover it up, meaning the account could land him in jail. "Rappers" was slang used only for a citizen who complained to law enforcement.

The Azerbaijani language also has its own expressions for criminal and thieving groups. Many of these phrases originated during the Soviet rule. At that time, people from different strata of society - peasants, intellectuals, merchants, officers, etc. different expressions have arisen as people fill the prisons. For example, the slang "to push an empty wagon" was created by miners and meant to talk nonsense. "Volına" - the word pistol comes from the Cossacks. The word "Jigan" means "to burn", "to burn". At first, the word "Jiqan" was used to refer to people who were burned with soot. Later, this word was used for cruel people, fraudsters, and swindlers. The word "Müftə" (xalyava) is a word borrowed from Poland. The word müftə here means the throat of a boot. Fraudsters wore long-necked boots and roamed the markets. One of the swindlers distracted the merchant, and the other threw the stolen goods down the boot's throat. This word is used in modern jargon in the sense of "free", "gift".

We can say that one of the areas most prone to the development of slangs in the language is the field of military service. The strength and meaning of their lexicons are closely related to the constant stress of strict discipline and sometimes the threat of war, as well as the closed, isolated nature of their daily lives. These slangs include "daisy pusher" meaning "a dead man", "N.B.G.", which is an abbreviation of "no bloody good", "(sadly out of luck)" "SOOL" with abbreviation can be an example.

Some of the slangs used in the English language also belong to the medical field. Most of the authors conducting research in this field have noted that the vast majority of words in the lexicon of medical professionals consist of abbreviations and acronyms. One of these

researchers, PC Colin, divides the lexicon of the medical field into two parts: slangs and abbreviations. "Knee jerk" - the abbreviation of the expression "KJ", "new born" - "NB" instead of the expression "sit out of bed", "SOOB" instead of the expression "sit out of bed", etc. is an example of such slang.

Slangs in the Azerbaijani language and their use are not among the topics that have been discussed a lot. Since this area has recently started to attract the attention of linguists and scientists, it has not been possible to investigate all areas yet. Although dictionaries related to slang words and phrases in British English and American English have been prepared, there is no work done in this direction in our country yet. For this reason, slangs related to medical and military service fields and a number of other fields have not yet been developed and revealed in our language.

CONCLUSION

At the end of numerous studies, it can be concluded that the similarities between the slangs in the Azerbaijani and English languages prevail over their differences. Both languages have the concept of slang and their explanations are compatible with each other. Therefore, the concept of slang is used in the same sense in both English and Azerbaijani languages. The forms of their formation are almost predominant. Similarity was also observed in the features of sentence usage and structural types.

Currently, there is a great need to study the slangs that exist in the Azerbaijani language. Because in order to speak any language, it is important to know its literary language as well as its colloquial language, and the importance of slangs in the colloquial language is undeniable. Especially among today's youth and teenagers, they have become an integral part of everyday conversation.

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